

Marginalized Groups Issues and Problems in Acquiring School Education and Higher Education - A Study on Malayali Tribes of Sitheri Hills

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Introduction

Marginalization is thus a complex as well as a very serious phenomenon. It can effectively push people to the margins of society, where their sense of security is in every way a threatened one. In India Social Groups in the Main stream are equipped with better access to power and privilege as opposed to marginalized. The latter are vulnerable and have remained exploited, degraded and deprived of access to the existing socio-economic resources. Education should be seen as a tool for the employment of the marginalized, as it leads to an expansion of choices, freedom and real opportunity. We must look beyond the traditional practice of education and attack the oppressive system inbuilt in this kind of educational system. It is only by respecting the sense of inquiry and questioning present in the young minds, can we empower them about a positive transformation.¹

What is Marginalization?

Marginalization – sometimes also called social exclusion, refers to the relegation to the fringes of society due to lack of access to rights, resources, and opportunities. It is a major cause of vulnerability, which refers to exposure to a range of possible harms, and being unable to deal with them adequately. In the context of INWORK, marginalized groups include people with experiences of Homelessness, Problematic substance use, (alcohol and drugs), Prison/ offending Mental health problems. In other words marginalized people might be socially, economically, politically, and legally ignored, excluded or neglected and therefore vulnerable to livelihood change. The people who are marginalized are outside the existing system of protection and integration. This limits their opportunities and means for survival.

The term defined marginalization can be in the following ways:

1. Peter Leonard defines: Marginality as being outside the mainstream of productive activity.
2. Ghana s gurung and Michael Kalmar mentions, “the concept of marginality is generally, used to analysis socio-economic, political and cultural spheres, where disadvantaged people struggle to gain access to resources and full participation in social life.”²

The Importance and Challenges to Acquire Higher Education in Marginalized Groups

Literacy is the stepping stone to social and economic empowerment, something India’s marginalized communities need desperately. Children from Marginalized Indian communities who are not exposed to literacy materials like books and stories, and formal access to language, reading, and writing development do not see brain development at par with their more privileged peers. A significant proportion of India’s children are unable to demonstrate even the most basic levels of reading achievement, something that has been noted prominently in children from poor families, scheduled castes and scheduled tribes and ethnic minority groups. Education and health are the most important drivers of India’s Social and economic development. According to world development report 1996 entitled, from plan to market “a well educated, healthy work force is essential for economic growth.”³

Functions of Education towards Individual

- Development of inborn potentialities,
- Modifying Behavior,
- All Round Development,

Functions of Education towards Society

- Social Change and Control
- Reconstruction of Experiences
- Development of Social and moral Value

Functions of Education towards Nation

- Inculcation of civic and social responsibility
- Training for Leadership
- National integration

Therefore, really education is an essential ingredient for all ages and stages of the life of an individual, society as well as the nation. Education can be real panacea for all social evils.⁴

Area of the Study

Tamilnadu is home to 36 Tribal communities. Dharmapuri District which has one of the largest tribal population nurtures five major tribal groups. Major tribe community is the Malayalis and around 90% of them belong to Sitheri Hills located in Eastern Ghats⁶. A Sitheri hill under Papireddipatti Taluk has 63 Villages inhabited by more than 11,000 tribes and topographically the area is undulating with an altitude varying from 240m to 1266m. Of the 63 villages in Sitheri hill area, 15 Villages have only proper road and infrastructure facility, resulting in limited mobility, and other Villages are devoid of transportation facilities hampering connectivity with the plains⁷.

The Life Style of Malayali Tribes in Sitheri Hills

Malayali tribal people lead a simple life with almost everyone dependent on agriculture cultivating different kind of grains, ragi, bhajra, maize, rice, sunflower, and fruit bearing trees. Their lifestyle is

accompanied by Low literacy levels, high levels of indebtedness, lack of awareness of basic rights which have led to their exploitation by middlemen in terms of bonded labour, illicit smuggling of red sanders, under utilization of government schemes and aversion towards development ending up in 90% of the tribal people are living the below poverty line. There has been systemic failure in giving tribals of Sitheri a stake in the modern economic processes, in assimilating with the mainstream for their betterment.⁸

Status of Acquiring Education in Sitheri Hills

1. Primary School – There were 9 primary schools out of 63 villages in Sitheri hills. Tholthooki and Jakkampatti. It is a common for these villages (Naduvalavu, Alagur). It links all other primary schools and those nine primary schools are giving education more than two villages. The following primary schools are giving education to their neighbouring villages. These are: Sitheri - Moolerikaadu, Mambarai - Oomathi, Nalamangadai, S.Ammapalayam - Mullai nagar, Shanmugapuram, Thathukanalli, Mithikaadu - paaraivalavu, Kundalmaduvu, Vellivalavu, Suriyakadai - Sulakurichi, Kattukottai, Thekkalpatti, Kalnaadu - Sekkizhithambur, Thulasikaadu, elanthankadai, Erumaikadai, Senkaatukollai.
 - All Primary Schools has severe paucity of teachers and most of the schools are single Teacher School and Sometimes, a single teacher is managing two schools at the same time. The school buildings have dilapidated conditions and absence of toilet facilities which made many schools to be closed and reopened repetitively. E.g. Suriyakadai, Elanthankadai village. Most of the teachers are coming from other Districts, the teachers are staying 40 - 50 Km distance from their respective schools and it takes nearly 2 hours, They have less awareness about culture of the tribals of Sitheri hills.⁹
2. Middle School- 9: There are 9 middle schools, Most of the middle schools have 2-5 teachers. The teachers are coming from other districts, everyday and they travel 60-70km daily. Middle schools are also giving providing education to more than two villages, it includes maximum seven villages. These are: Pereri - Thazh Paaraivalavu, MerPaaraivalavu, Pereri Puthur - Paaraivalavu, Mullikaadu, Kundampatti, Velankaadu, Kalasapaadi - Aalamarathuvalavu, Tharisukaadu, Akkaraikaadu, Karukkampatti Velampalli - jalloothu, Arasanatham - Nunavalavu, Puliyamarathuvalavu, Kinattruvalavu, Kottakaadu, Nochikottai, Mannur - Nadukollai, Melmannur, Thaazh Mannur, nadumannur, Govindankadai, Mettuvalavu, maangadai, Selur - Senkaadu, Kullampatti, Kanathaampatti.
3. High School (2) - There are two high schools in Sitheri hills. Ammapalayam (2018) high school has a proper infrastructure facility in Sitheri hills. There are 6-7 teachers appointed. It has well accommodation and proper road facilities. This school also resulted 100% in SSLC examinations. This high school is the habitation of these villages Nadukollai, Melmannur, Thaazh Mannur, Nadumannur, Govindankadai, Mettuvalavu, maangadai, Selur, Senkaadu, Kullampatti, Kanathaampatti, Sekkizhithambur, Thulasikaadu, elanthankadai, Erumaikadai, Senkaatukollai. Kalasapaadi is the another high school of sitherihills and it established 1st june 2019. But it doesn't have proper infrastructure facility. It is habitation control of following villages: Aalamarathuvalavu, Tharisukaadu, Akkaraikaadu, Karukkampatti, Velampalli, jalloothu, Arasanatham, Nunavalavu, Puliyamarathuvalavu, Kinattruvalavu, Kottakaadu.¹⁰
 - Higher Secondary School – There are only one higher secondary school all over 63 villages in Sitheri hills. While comparing to other schools of Sitheri hills, this school has proper infrastructure facility, but minimal number of teachers(5) are working here. This school had only one boys and girls hostel with limited seats. Non availability of the seats of the girl's hostel, there are many instances of sexual abuse and assault of girl students on their way

to school by their community men. Safety for girls travelling a long distance for education is uncertain in that region this eventually leads to stopping of girl children from attending schools and in turn to early marriage. On a brief note, educating girl children poses a huge struggle to the parents.

- In general during their journey to school both students and teachers met many problems like sexual abuses, robbery, fear about snakes and gaur in hills and etc. and there are no proper infrastructure facilities like toilets in schools, roads, electricity, water for drinking and using all other activities, accommodation for teachers and comfortable journey. It's very hard to reach the school during rainy times, because it causes accidents to them.
- In Sitheri hills, regional variation also exists to achieve the higher education. There only 15 villages had road facilities like Tholthuki, Pereri, Pereri Puthur, Suriyakadai, Sulakurichi, Kattukottai, Selur, Ammapalayam, Nochikottai, Thekkalpatti, Shanmugapuram, Paaraivalavu, Kundampatti, Moolerikaadu, Mannur. Due to availability of road facilities, proper infrastructure facilities are developed in those villages. Regional variation in higher education is also caused by these infrastructure facilities around the villages of sitherihills.
- Sitheri village awarded 2018 open defecation free village, But Sitheri panchayat schools like kalnaadu, Suriyakadai, sellur, kalasapaadi villages don't have proper toilet facilities. So the girls students met many problems to complete their school education.
- Sitheri hills also have tribal welfare schools following villages, there are pere, arasanatham, mannur, maangadai, velampalli, Sitheri, kalnaadu, nochikottai, kalasapaadi, Jakkampatti, tholthuki, Suriyakadai. The tribal welfare schools provides bedsheet, food, 3-4 uniform sets, chappal, shoes, shutter, notebooks and etc for students wealth. But there were only limited teachers. This kind of school system in Sitheri hills, are increasing students strength in all the tribal schools. Comparatively it is better than the other schools.
- There are E.R.K arts and Science College for women in Erumiyampatti, Annai arts and science college in Nambipatti, Muthusamy arts and science college in Harur, P.D.R.V arts and Science College in Jakkampatti. And these colleges are giving education to first generation people who wish to pursue their higher education last five years after the completion of their higher secondary studies in Sitheri hills. The girl children also studied here, comparatively the ratio of getting higher education of girls are less than boys, because, Parents are not encouraging the study of their girl children.¹¹

Observation by the Researcher

- Very limited availability of teachers comparatively for the number of the students, less working hours of the school keeps the education quality at a low level. Increasing the number of Skillful teachers, improvement in infrastructure, better utilization of technology for running smart classes, standard school working hours maintenance can increase the standard of education.
- Already commendable job is done by Blessing Youth Mission in imparting quality education to the tribes by running a middle school in Moolerikaadu village with necessary infrastructure and accommodation facilities in addition to the guidance for the students to pursue higher education and job opportunities. Extension of these missionary activities to all villages will in debatably bear fruitful results in raising educational standard that will ultimately raise the community standard as well.¹²
- Many students have to walk for 5 to 15 km to reach the respective schools hindering their continuous attendance to school. Villages like Jalloothu, Villamballi, Thulasikaadu, Erumakadai and Elanthankadai villages don't even have primary schools. Students of Kalnaadu, Manoor, Arasanatham, and Kalasapadi have to walk for 10-15 Km for higher secondary education.

- Insufficient schools affects the Quality of the education whereas very limited availability of teachers comparatively for the number of the students, less working hours of the school immensely affect the quality of the education. So the government make suitable step to provide accommodation facilities and bus facility to the teachers.
- There are many instances of sexual abuse and assault of girl students on their way to school by their community men. Safety for girls travelling a long distance for education is uncertain in that region and this eventually leads to stopping of girl children from attending schools and in turn to early marriage. If the Government increase the hostel facility for girl children, it will help to pursue the higher education.
- Most of the primary and middle schools in Sitheri hills don't have drop outs, but higher secondary have dropouts due to lack of awareness about higher education and their parents forced to sent cattle rearing, and other menial jobs like cotton mills in thirupur,Coimbatore, tea estate in Ooty and plantation works etc to their children.¹³
- Every village in Sitheri hills has 30% of people going to agricultural works, another 70% going to out of villages for jobs like construction labourers, cotton mill works in Coimbatore and thirupur etc. So most of the children are under the control of their grand parents, due to lack of parental care, the children's are involved social crimes like drink addiction in early age starting from 8th std, sexual abuse of girl children, school drop outs and going to illegal cutting of red sanders in andhira Pradesh etc. if panchayat take suitable steps to create awareness about their livelihood opportunities and education it will reduce social crimes and illiteracy in Sitheri hills.
- There is more availability of B.Ed graduates in Pereri , Ammapalayam and Sitheri villages, due to lack of employment opportunities they also going to illegal cutting of red sanders in Andhirapadesh, so they can be well utilized for the teaching purposes with the help of community participation.
- Until 2010 through SSA sufficient funds were to provide for infrastructure developments which were reduced to 10,000 to 22,000 in later years which are abysmally low when compared to their demands of Schools in Sitheri hills. More funds need to be allocated by the government for infrastructure development of schools and arrangement of public transport during school hours would be much useful to the students.¹⁴
- In 2018 The Srinivaasa charitable trust is doing a commendable role in that region by appointing their own teachers for taking care of slow learners in schools, providing necessary inventories, renovation of buildings and toilets, and the trust is ready to construct school buildings by taking responsibility for 90% of the cost. Sitheri Panchayat should take necessary steps to arrange for the remaining 10% in order to meet the infrastructure needs, and also take suitable step to approach the trust to appoint the teachers in 2019 for the schools to increase quality of education in Sitheri hills.
- Though projectors, computers, Teaching Learning Materials are given to them through SSA, they remain idle due to lack of technical skills among teachers. The available educated youths in that region can be used for the technical guidance to use the electric gadgets to improve their learning skills.
- In higher secondary school, they got 100% pass percentage last year with help of their limited teachers and students had awareness about higher education and 90% of the student pursued their higher education nearby colleges like nursing, arts and science and law. But they met many problems due to unfavorable climatic conditions. So the government establish the colleges like diploma courses, Art and science and polytechnic college for the welfare of tribals of Sitheri hills.¹⁵

Conclusion

Human Rights Watch said, Marginalized Groups continue to face discrimination in India despite constitutional Guarantees and laws prohibiting discrimination, As per the view of Dr.A.P.J. Abdulkalm, Education is the engine of economic growth and social change. It Creates motivation for progress and brings revolution in the ideas necessary for progress of the country. It teaches honesty, inspires patriotism, enhances social prestige and promotes economic development. When people are educated, we not only get teachers, professionals and executives but more importantly citizens who are aware, sensitive and responsible. It makes people place social good above personal gains. Not only this , it transforms a human being into a wholesome whole, a noble soul and an asset to the universe. Sitheri hills people are one of the marginalized groups in Dharmapuri district. The total literacy rate of Dharmapuri district is 68.54%. but Sitheri hills literacy rate is 52%. The government should take suitable steps to improve the status of education and the betterment of their life.

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